

FNS - Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Existing food nutrition security data, knowledge, and tools for health and agri-food sciences although widespread are fragmented, lack critical mass, and access is 'unevenly' distributed for users. This means data are not readily found, accessible, interoperable or reusable (FAIR), and existing services focus on clinical, molecular or biological sciences. FNS-Cloud will bring about change through standards, demonstrators, services and FAIRer food nutrition security data.

FNS-Cloud objectives are to:

- Implement and test FNS-Cloud, as related to technical aspects of access and re-use of datasets and/ or tools.
- Create, integrate, and test FNS-Cloud Services related to interoperability and standardisation as well as providing training and support for users.
- Integrate existing and emerging FNS datasets, sources, and formats
- Develop a governance model and business operations to support sustainability and add value for prior public investment.

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FNS-Cloud is developing the first-generation 'food cloud' by federating existing and emerging datasets and developing and integrating services to support re-use through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

www.fns-cloud.eu

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<https://bit.ly/2PNJRhz>

FNS-Cloud will:

- Launch three Demonstrators (agri-food, nutrition and lifestyle, and non-communicable diseases and the human microbiome) allowing sophisticated analysis, visualisation, and interpretation for future FNS research and exploitation of knowledge leading to a sustainable food system.
- Publish recommendations/ guidelines and standards for data exchange and comparisons, and deploy or improve application programming interfaces (APIs) for access and re-use of data by FNS user communities.
- Implement an Open Science and Open Innovation framework (governance) and sustainable business model, addressing uneven access and fragmentation, leading to easier access to FNS datasets and tools.
- Deliver training and support to boost confidence and skills in exploitation as well as increasing awareness of the benefits for capturing knowledge and improving professional practice.

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Short-term (2025)

- Enhance management of FNS datasets, access to tools and services, skills and confidence amongst FNS researchers, and engagement with other e-infrastructures in Europe and beyond.
- Exploit proven governance and business models based on best practices, global standards, and policy.

Medium-term (by 2030)

- Improve data (management and exploitation) skills and increased awareness of the benefits of Open Science amongst FNS researchers through work-based training, online resources, and targeted dissemination.

Longer-term (2030 onwards)

- Increase data sharing and reuse amongst FNS researchers and dialogue with user communities.
- Advance existing ICT tools and service solutions from (technology readiness level) TRLO-4 to TRL7-9.

